

Agreeing to Disagree: Understanding Resolution Misalignments in Video Games

Online Appendix

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Abstract

Software bugs are typically treated as defects that should be fixed to improve correctness, reliability, and user experience. In video games, this does not always hold: some behaviours intentionally designed by developers may disrupt players and be experienced as bugs, while behaviours developers consider unexpected may become useful, enjoyable, or meaningful aspects of gameplay that players prefer to preserve rather than remove. As a result, developer decisions may diverge from community expectations: developers may fix bugs that players value or leave disruptive bugs unresolved. We define such mismatches between developer decisions and community expectations as *resolution misalignments*. These misalignments can frustrate players and damage a game’s reputation. Understanding their prevalence and underlying patterns is therefore important to make informed decisions about bug-resolution.

In this paper, we conduct a large-scale empirical study of resolution misalignments in *Minecraft*. We curate a dataset of 10,788 bug reports and 5,837 player feedback posts related to these reports. We derive developers’ resolution decisions from bug reports and infer players’ expectations about whether bugs should be fixed or preserved from community posts. By comparing these decisions and expectations, we find that 61.2% of bug reports with a clear player expectation are misaligned with developer decisions, and that 93.0% of these misalignments are the cases where players expected a fix but developers explicitly decide not to fix the bug. Our characterization of such misalignments shows that many of the misaligned closed bug reports are resolved as working as intended. Additionally, a non-negligible proportion of misalignments arise when developers fix buggy behaviours that players wanted to preserve, often surfacing as community requests to revert the fix. To support developers in anticipating resolution misalignments before final bug-resolution decisions are made, we propose Misfit, an approach for predicting community misalignment. Overall, our findings show that player expectations introduce a clear, yet often overlooked, dimension of bug resolution in video games.

1 (RQ3) Resolution misalignment by Minecraft Edition

Table 1: Resolution Intent Matrix by Minecraft edition on the matched bug report–community post pairs.

Community expectation	Java F	Java NF	Bedrock F	Bedrock NF
Expected to fix	1,749 (31.9%)	2,884 (52.6%)	1,312 (24.7%)	3,048 (57.5%)
Expected to preserve	227 (4.1%)	405 (7.4%)	218 (4.1%)	571 (10.8%)
Not mentioned	76 (1.4%)	142 (2.6%)	68 (1.3%)	88 (1.7%)
Total	5,483		5,305	

F = Fixed, NF = Not fixed.

2 (RQ3) Resolution misalignment by VGBT category

Table 2: Resolution Intent Matrix by VGBT category on the matched bug report–community post pairs ($N = 10,788$).

Community expectation	Network		Other		Balance		Temporal		Sound		Non-temp.		Impl. resp.		Navig.		Crash	
	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF	F	NF
Expected to fix	33 (9.1%)	302 (83.7%)	11 (5.0%)	168 (75.7%)	79 (23.4%)	217 (64.4%)	44 (24.0%)	108 (59.0%)	93 (33.8%)	151 (54.9%)	2,239 (30.1%)	3,991 (53.6%)	499 (28.2%)	897 (50.7%)	40 (31.2%)	67 (52.3%)	23 (35.9%)	31 (48.4%)
Expected to preserve	3 (0.8%)	17 (4.7%)	5 (2.3%)	32 (14.4%)	14 (4.2%)	20 (5.9%)	4 (2.2%)	18 (9.8%)	14 (5.1%)	7 (2.5%)	313 (4.2%)	648 (8.7%)	86 (4.9%)	218 (12.3%)	6 (4.7%)	9 (7.0%)	0 (0.0%)	7 (10.9%)
Not mentioned	3 (0.8%)	3 (0.8%)	2 (0.9%)	4 (1.8%)	2 (0.6%)	5 (1.5%)	0 (0.0%)	9 (4.9%)	6 (2.2%)	4 (1.5%)	102 (1.4%)	155 (2.1%)	25 (1.4%)	45 (2.5%)	3 (2.3%)	3 (2.3%)	1 (1.6%)	2 (3.1%)
Total	361		222		337		183		275		7,448		1,770		128		64	

F = Fixed, NF = Not fixed.

3 Retrieval performance across encoders and retrieval methods.

Table 3: Retrieval performance across encoders and retrieval methods ($n = 66$ ground-truth queries, no similarity threshold). Avg@ k = mean cosine similarity of the top- k retrieved candidates; reported as “—” for Hybrid RRF (scores are RRF ranks, not cosine).

Encoder	Method	H@1	H@2	H@3	H@4	H@5	H@6	H@7	H@8	H@9	H@10	MRR	Avg@1	Avg@3	Avg@5	Avg@10
nomic-v1.5	Cosine	0.6364	0.6818	0.6818	0.6818	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6653	0.8306	0.7919	0.7752	0.7549
nomic-v1.5	ANN-HNSW	0.6364	0.6818	0.6818	0.6818	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6647	0.8306	0.7919	0.7752	0.7549
arctic-1	Hybrid RRF	0.6061	0.6667	0.6970	0.6970	0.7121	0.7121	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.6547	—	—	—	—
nomic-v1.5	Hybrid RRF	0.5909	0.6667	0.6818	0.6818	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.6970	0.7273	0.6413	—	—	—	—
bge-m3	Hybrid RRF	0.5909	0.6515	0.6515	0.6667	0.6818	0.6818	0.6970	0.6970	0.7121	0.7273	0.6359	—	—	—	—
gte-large	Hybrid RRF	0.5758	0.6515	0.6970	0.6970	0.7121	0.7121	0.7121	0.7121	0.7273	0.7273	0.6360	—	—	—	—
arctic-1	Cosine	0.5606	0.6515	0.6970	0.7121	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7424	0.6312	0.6468	0.5929	0.5705	0.5431
arctic-1	ANN-HNSW	0.5606	0.6515	0.6970	0.7121	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7424	0.6306	0.6468	0.5929	0.5705	0.5430
multitqa-mpnet	Hybrid RRF	0.5606	0.6515	0.6667	0.6667	0.6970	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7273	0.7424	0.6250	—	—	—	—
bge-m3	Cosine	0.5606	0.6212	0.6364	0.6667	0.6667	0.6818	0.6970	0.6970	0.7121	0.7273	0.6138	0.7669	0.7213	0.7015	0.6772

4 (C2) Evaluation

4.1 The full list of features

Table 4: The 15 engineered tabular features concatenated with each text embedding to form the model input. Features fall into seven numeric counters and eight binary indicators. All feature values are computed from the raw Mojira issue tracker records when available, with a text-derived fallback used when the raw metadata is missing.

Feature	Description	Type
<i>Numeric counters (7)</i>		
<code>attachment_count</code>	total number of files attached to the bug report	int
<code>n_attach_images</code>	number of image attachments (<code>.png</code> , <code>.jpg</code> , <code>.jpeg</code> , <code>.gif</code> , <code>.webp</code>)	int
<code>n_attach_videos</code>	number of video attachments (<code>.mp4</code> , <code>.mov</code> , <code>.webm</code> , <code>.mkv</code> , <code>.avi</code>)	int
<code>n_affected_versions</code>	number of game versions listed in the <i>Affects Versions</i> field	int
<code>description_word_count</code>	word count of the free-text description	int
<code>description_char_count</code>	character count of the free-text description	int
<code>n_repro_steps</code>	number of enumerated reproduction steps extracted from the description	int
<i>Binary indicators (8)</i>		
<code>has_video</code>	1 if at least one video attachment is present	{0,1}
<code>has_repro_steps</code>	1 if the description contains enumerated reproduction steps	{0,1}
<code>has_code_block</code>	1 if the description contains a fenced code block or Jira <code>{code}/noformat</code> marker	{0,1}
<code>is_mcpe</code>	1 if the report is filed against Minecraft Bedrock Edition (MCPE)	{0,1}
<code>has_platform</code>	1 if the <i>Platform</i> field is populated	{0,1}
<code>is_mobile_platform</code>	1 if the platform is Android, iOS, Amazon, Chromebook, Fire OS, or similar	{0,1}
<code>is_console_platform</code>	1 if the platform is Xbox, PlayStation, or Nintendo Switch	{0,1}
<code>is_pc_platform</code>	1 if the platform is Windows, macOS, or Linux	{0,1}

4.2 The full list of models

Table 5: Model architectures evaluated in the sweep, grouped by family. Each architecture is annotated with its corresponding methodological reference.

Family	Architectures and references
Linear & kernel	<code>lr_l1</code> [1], <code>lr_l2</code> [1], <code>ridge</code> [2], <code>sgd</code> [3], <code>linear_svm</code> [4], <code>calibrated_svm</code> [5]
Instance-based	<code>knn</code> [6], <code>gaussian_nb</code> [7]
Trees / boosting	<code>rf</code> [8], <code>extratrees</code> [9], <code>balanced_rf</code> [10], <code>xgb</code> [11], <code>lgbm</code> [12], <code>hgb</code> [12], <code>catboost</code> [13], <code>gbm</code> [14], <code>adaboost</code> [15], <code>rusboost</code> [16], <code>balanced_bagging</code> [17], <code>bagging_xgb</code> [11, 17], <code>easy_ensemble</code> [18]
Feed-forward MLPs	<code>mlp_small</code> [19], <code>mlp_wide</code> [19], <code>mlp_deep</code> [19], <code>mlp_dropout</code> [20], <code>mlp_resnet</code> [21], <code>mlp_mixer</code> [22], <code>res_mlp</code> [23], <code>wide_deep</code> [24], <code>snn</code> [25], <code>prenet</code> [26]
Attention / transformer	<code>attn_mlp</code> [27], <code>tabular_transformer</code> [28], <code>ft_transformer</code> [29], <code>transformer</code> [27], <code>gated_resnet</code> [30], <code>tabnet</code> [31]
Sequence	<code>lstm</code> [32], <code>gru</code> [33], <code>bilstm_attn</code> [34], <code>cnn_lstm</code> [35], <code>cnn_transformer</code> [27, 35]
1D-CNN	<code>textcnn</code> [36], <code>resnet1d</code> [21], <code>convnext1d</code> [37], <code>densenet1d</code> [38], <code>inception1d</code> [39], <code>senet1d</code> [40], <code>unet1d</code> [41]
Anomaly / self-supervised	<code>autoencoder</code> [42], <code>deepsad</code> [43], <code>devnet</code> [44]
Foundation model	<code>tabpfn</code> [45]

Table 6: Text embedding models used to encode bug reports. Every configuration concatenates one of these representations with the 15 engineered tabular features.

Embedding	Source / family	Dim.	Notes
<code>gte-large</code>	Alibaba GTE Large	1024	general-purpose sentence encoder
<code>nomi-v1.5</code>	Nomic AI v1.5	768	standard context length
<code>nomi-v1.5-long</code>	Nomic AI v1.5	768	long-context variant
<code>bge-m3</code>	BAAI BGE-M3	1024	multi-lingual / multi-granularity
<code>bge-m3-long</code>	BAAI BGE-M3	1024	long-context variant
<code>bge-small</code>	BAAI BGE Small	384	compact model
<code>arctic-l</code>	Snowflake Arctic Embed L	1024	retrieval-optimised
<code>tfidf</code>	TF-IDF (sparse baseline)	-	statistical, non-neural baseline

Table 7: Class-imbalance handling strategies. The first eight are applied on the main grid (`windows_benchmark`); the last three are additional SMOTE variants explored in the targeted `push_bal_acc` sweep.

Strategy	Description
<code>none</code>	no re-balancing (baseline)
<code>class_weight</code>	inverse-frequency loss weighting
<code>oversample</code>	random over-sampling of the minority class
<code>undersample</code>	random under-sampling of the majority class
<code>smote</code>	Synthetic Minority Over-sampling Technique [46]
<code>adasyn</code>	Adaptive Synthetic sampling [47]
<code>smote_tomek</code>	SMOTE followed by Tomek-link cleaning
<code>smote_enn</code>	SMOTE followed by Edited-Nearest-Neighbour cleaning
<code>borderline_smote</code>	Borderline SMOTE (samples near the class boundary) [48]
<code>svm_smote</code>	SVM-guided SMOTE (uses support vectors to steer synthesis)
<code>kmeans_smote</code>	KMeans SMOTE (cluster-aware synthesis)

Table 8: Top 20 results of 854 model training experiments

#	Model	Configuration	Embedding	Acc.	MCC	Bal. Acc.	AUPRC	AUROC
<i>Top-3 configurations with <code>nomi-v1.5</code> / <code>nomi-v1.5-long</code> embeddings</i>								
1	AttentionMLP [27]	<code>attn_mlp_focal_mixup_swa</code>	<code>nomi-v1.5</code>	0.776	0.331	0.683	0.394	0.710
2	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_mi500</code>	<code>nomi-v1.5-long</code>	0.794	0.326	0.668	0.390	0.700
3	ResMLP [23]	<code>res_mlp_bagging5seeds</code>	<code>nomi-v1.5</code>	0.776	0.322	0.677	0.399	0.724
<i>Strongest configurations with other embeddings (val. MCC < 0.322)</i>								
4	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_pca100</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.766	0.306	0.670	0.390	0.697
5	MLP-Mixer [22]	<code>mlp_mixer_enhanced_weighted_smooth</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.773	0.300	0.662	0.384	0.702
6	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_mi200</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.768	0.295	0.662	0.389	0.678
7	TabNet [31]	<code>tabnet tab+gte-large undersample gap=GAP2</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	-	0.291	0.683	0.387	0.701
8	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_borderline_smote</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.765	0.290	0.660	0.398	0.709
9	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_smote_enn_v2</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.741	0.288	0.668	0.375	0.695
10	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_pca200</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.718	0.286	0.673	0.371	0.702
11	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_svm_smote</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.696	0.283	0.676	0.404	0.707
12	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_pca50</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.754	0.279	0.657	0.385	0.686
13	ResMLP [23]	<code>res_mlp_bagging5seeds</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.760	0.279	0.654	0.387	0.696
14	AttentionMLP [27]	<code>attn_mlp_weighted_smooth</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.635	0.274	0.677	0.390	0.724
15	ExtraTrees [9]	<code>extratrees_smote_tomek_v2</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.706	0.272	0.666	0.399	0.705
16	ResMLP [23]	<code>res_mlp_weighted_smooth</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.796	0.270	0.627	0.383	0.660
17	TabNet [31]	<code>tabnet tab+gte-large smote gap=GAP2</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	-	0.270	0.675	0.446	0.743
18	RandomForest [8]	<code>rf_tuned_1000</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.766	0.269	0.645	0.364	0.679
19	XGBoost [11]	<code>xgb_tuned_deep</code>	<code>gte-large</code>	0.636	0.266	0.672	0.367	0.696
20	GatedResNet [30]	<code>gated_resnet tab+bge-m3 smote_enn gap=GAP2</code>	<code>bge-m3</code>	-	0.264	0.672	0.346	0.702

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